

Only W1263 and ARC6605 of group I showed resistant (R) reaction. Differentials of the other three groups showed a consistent susceptible (S) reaction (see table), thus depicting a new R-S-S-S type

response, which had not been previously reported in India. In supplementary studies, the Iroisemba population did not mate with any of the biotypes. We therefore propose

that this be considered a distinct biotype, 3M, that is different from the biotype 3 prevalent in Bihar (Ranchi) and Andhra Pradesh (Jagtiyal). ■

Pest resistance—other pests

Selection for weed competitiveness in upland rice

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Weed infestation is a major problem in upland and hydromorphic rice ecosystems in West Africa. Weeding is generally by hand, but in many cases effective weed control is impossible due to a shortage of labor. One way to reduce weed control inputs (hand weeding or herbicides) is to use weed-competitive cultivars to suppress and/or tolerate weeds. We conducted two experiments in 1994 to identify such cultivars.

In the first experiment, 16 promising cultivars selected in 1993 for their ability to suppress or tolerate weeds were evaluated under high-, medium-, and low-input management at M'be in Côte d'Ivoire. The experiment was laid out using a split-plot design with three replications and management levels as the main plot and varieties as the subplot.

Two *Oryza glaberrima* varieties, CG14 and CG20, gave the most tillers and leaf area under all levels of management. They had rapid vegetative growth and their plots had low weed biomass at 18 and 40 d after sowing (DAS) (see figure). Tall *O. sativa* varieties with high tillering ability such as WAB96-1-1 and SP4, suppressed weed growth. A third group, WAB181-18, WAB56-50, and WAB56-125, with high tillering ability, large leaf area, and intermediate stature (90-100 cm), tolerated weeds during the ripening stage. These cultivars had superior yields and were selected for detailed studies on weed competitiveness in 1995.

In a second experiment, 12 *O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima* lines, previously selected to form a range of distinctly different plant types for plant height, tillering capacity, and

Relationship between tiller number and weed dry weight (wdw) under low (a, b) and medium (c) inputs.

*1 = CG20, 2 = CGN, 3 = WAB56-50, 4 = WAB181-18, 5 = WAB56-104, 6 = WAB56-125, 7 = WAB96-1-1, 8 = IRAT144, 9 = WABC165, 10 = SP4, 11 = WAB99-1-1, 12 = IDSA10, 13 = ITAS257, 14 = IAC164, 15 = IRAT112, and 16 = CNA4136.

leaf type, were grown under two levels of weed control. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design with three replications and a plot size of 4 × 2.6 m.

Weed biomass at rice maturity differed among the varieties. There were interactions ($P < 0.003$) between weeding regime and cultivar for grain yield. Regression analysis across varieties and replicates showed that

grain yield from weedy plots, expressed as a proportion of yield from the clean-weeded plots, was negatively correlated with weed weight at rice maturity ($r = 0.62$, $n = 36$) and positively correlated with rice root length at 49 DAS (0.79), and tiller number (0.75) and leaf area (0.73) at 36 DAS. These results are further evidence of the association between crop development during its vegetative phase and competitiveness with weeds.

More studies will be conducted to confirm the factors that determine differences among eleven cultivars in weed competitiveness. Promising cultivars will be used in a breeding program and further evaluated for yield potential. ■

Stress tolerance—drought

Genetic variability of osmotic adjustment under drought stress in rice

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Drought is the major abiotic stress limiting rice yield in the rainfed lowland and upland ecosystems. Little progress has been made in incorporating tolerance for drought into rice. Understanding the physiological mechanism and their genetic basis will be helpful in developing selection strategies for improving drought tolerance in rice.

Osmotic adjustment as a process of active solute accumulation under drought stress is receiving increasing attention as an important component of drought tolerance in crop plants (Blum 1989, Ludlow and Muchow 1990). Osmotic adjustment results from the accumulation of solutes within cells, which lowers the osmotic potential and helps maintain turgor of both shoots and roots as plants experience water deficit stress. By using osmotic adjustment as a trait in dryland crop breeding programs, prospects are good for increasing potential yield and stabilizing yield under drought, as demonstrated in wheat (Morgan and

Condon 1986) and sorghum (Ludlow et al 1990).

The objective of our study was to identify the extent of genetic variation for osmotic adjustment in cultivated rice grown under drought stress. Twelve cultivars representing a range of germplasm from traditional dryland types to improved rainfed lowland types were studied under greenhouse conditions. Plants were grown in large PVC containers using a potting soil mixture. Water was withheld from 50 d after sowing to induce drought stress.

Changes in leaf osmotic potential and relative water content were measured every other day from initiation of stress until the plants wilted. The entire drought period was about 35 d. Osmotic adjustment was calculated following the method described by Morgan (1992). Results indicated large genetic variation for osmotic adjustment among the cultivars. The cultivar IR62266 expressed higher osmotic adjustment (1.76 MPa) than the rest. The cultivars Azucena, CT9993, Moroberekan, and IR52561 showed lower osmotic adjustment with values of 0.86, 0.81, 0.80, and 0.50 MPa, respectively.

Despite the positive influence of osmotic adjustment as a drought tolerance mechanism, the adoption of this trait in breeding programs for crop improvement has been slow. Among other reasons, the inability to rapidly and precisely screen large breeding populations for osmotic adjustment limits progress toward using this trait as a selection criterion. Screening for osmotic adjustment currently requires time-consuming complex measurement procedures. Identifying molecular markers (such as restriction fragment length polymorphism) linked to osmotic adjustment may provide plant breeders with a new tool for selecting cultivars with higher osmotic adjustment capacity.

The present study showed large genetic variation for osmotic adjustment that offers a good possibility for identifying suitable molecular markers for this trait in rice. Some of the genotypes tested in the study are parents of recombinant inbred and doubled-haploid line mapping populations that are being developed in collaboration with IRRI scientists for tagging genes associated with drought-adaptive traits.

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Stress tolerance—excess water

Characterization of the pyruvate decarboxylase gene family of rice and its potential application to submergence tolerance

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Flash flooding is one of the major causes of mass destruction of rice in many countries in Southeast Asia. Flooding produces anaerobic conditions because gases diffuse more slowly in water than in air.

Under anoxia, alcoholic fermentation occurs at rapid rates during submergence. In maize, the two key enzymes, pyruvate decarboxylase (PDC) and alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH), show higher activities under anoxia (Baily-Serres et al 1988). Only minimal levels of ADH are required for ethanol production in maize